

ULTRASONIC CHARACTERISATION AND MULTI-SCALE MODELLING OF THE DAMAGE UNDER TENSILE LOADING OF A 3D WOVEN SiC/SiC COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Thanks to their good thermo-mechanical properties, Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) are attractive materials for high temperature applications. They are planned to be used for hot parts in aircraft engines as an alternative to metallic solutions. Herakles (SAFRAN group) has developed a 3D woven SiC/SiC with a self-healing matrix for turbines of next generation engines. The microstructure can be separated through different scales: i) the scale of the fibre with a diameter of about ten microns, ii) the scale of the yarns formed of about five hundred fibres, iii) the scale of the woven perform resulting from the interleaving of the different yarns (Fig. 1). The matrix has multiple layers of Si-B-C to confer a protective behaviour against oxidation at high temperatures [1].

Damage in ceramic matrix composites subjected to a mechanical loading results from the growth of micro-

-cracks at different scales. These cracks induce a non-linear stress-strain behaviour and a degradation of the stiffness tensor. The ultrasonic measurement of all the components of the stiffness tensor during a tensile test provides access to the 3D macroscopic damage evolution [2]. Two modes of fracture have been identified [3]: matrix cracks oriented perpendicularly to the load direction and interfacial debonding.

The aim of this paper is to characterise the multi-scale damage of a 3D SiC/SiC composite. We present successively the ultrasonic measurement method, the experimental results from a tensile test, followed by their confrontation with the predictions based on a numerical multi-scale model. The comparison between the stiffness tensor identified from acoustic measurements and the one obtained by a multi-scale modelling confirms the orientation of cracks, their kinetic and their impact on the mechanical properties of the damaged material.

Fig. 1. Micrograph of a cross section of the 3D-SiC/SiC composite: (a) fibre, (b) porosity, (c) longitudinal yarn and (d) transverse yarns.

2 Ultrasonic determination of the stiffness tensor

In order to consider the tridimensional non-linear mechanical behaviour of the studied CMC, the variation of the stiffness tensor components is chosen as the damage variable [4]. The stiffness tensor takes particular forms depending on the material symmetry. Due to the orthotropy of the CMC sample, the stiffness tensor possesses nine independent non-zero components.

2.1 Ultrasonic waves in immersed plate

The ultrasonic evaluation of material stiffnesses consists of collecting speeds of waves propagating in various directions in the solid. The acquisitions are conducted in three incident planes (Fig. 2) corresponding to the planes (X_1, X_2) , (X_1, X_3) and (X_1, X_Ψ) , where $\mathbf{R} = (X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is the coordinate system and Ψ is the azimuthal angle equal to 45° . Wave speed measurements are performed by comparing ultrasonic pulses propagating in water with pulses which are refracted by a plate-like sample immersed in water [5]. Under small strains, the Christoffel equation, relating the mechanical properties (stiffness tensor) of an equivalent homogeneous media to the speeds of elastic bulk waves, is written as:

$$|\mathbf{\Gamma} - \rho V^2 \mathbf{I}| = 0, \quad (1)$$

with $\Gamma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} n_k n_l$ ($i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3$) and where ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{n} is the unit vector along the wave propagation direction, V is the wave speed (phase velocity) of ultrasonic waves, C_{ijkl} are the stiffness components and \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor. Generally, three modes propagate along the direction \mathbf{n} with different speeds and polarizations (Fig. 3): one quasi-longitudinal mode (QL) and two quasi-transverse modes (QT1) and (QT2). If the incident plane coincides with a plane of symmetry, only two waves are generated (one quasi-longitudinal and one quasi-transverse).

Fig. 2. Incident planes of the sample with parallel faces, defined by the azimuthal angle Ψ ($= 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ or 90°).

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of elastic bulk waves propagating through an immersed plate-like sample

By inverting equation (1), the stiffness components can be determined from a suitable set of experimental speeds collected in various directions. Usually, the stiffness tensor is determined by a Newton-Raphson algorithm [5]. Due to the specific properties of the considered samples of SiC/SiC, such as the low value of the critical angles for the quasi-longitudinal mode, a more suitable optimisation method was developed [6]. A genetic algorithm is used and adapted to our problem. This identification method is enough robust to identify the overall stiffness tensor by considering simultaneously all the incident planes.

The algorithm seeks the components C_{ij} (in reduced notation) by minimising the shift between the model responses $V_r(C_{ij}, \mathbf{n})$ and the experimental values $V_e(\mathbf{n}(\theta_r))$. The model responses are calculated using the Christoffel equation (1). The sought components are the solutions of the following minimisation problem:

$$(C_{ij}) = \min F_e(C_{ij}) \quad \text{with } u < C_{ij} < v$$

and

$$F_e(C_{ij}) = \sum_m \sum_{r=1}^N |V_t^{(1,m)}(C_{ij}, \mathbf{n}_r) - V_e^{(1,m)}(\mathbf{n}_r(\theta_r))|^2,$$

where u and v are the boundaries imposed to the components of the stiffness tensor. N is the number of experimental data collected in each incident plane, \mathbf{n}_r is the unit vector in the wave propagation direction and θ_r is the refracted angle. (X_1, X_m) stands for the incident plane ($m = 2, 3$ or 45°). The initial constraints u and v , on the diagonal components of the stiffness tensor, are defined from contact measurements previously performed [7]. A confidence interval, based on a statistical criterion, is associated with each identified stiffnesses.

2.2 Ultrasonic determination of the stiffness tensor under loading

Understanding and monitoring the damage of strongly anisotropic CMC is essential to formulate constitutive equations. By using an ultrasonic device coupled to a tensile machine (Fig. 4), all the components of the stiffness tensor can be identified during a mechanical test [2]. An extensometer, placed on the sample edge, provides the stress-strain curve at room temperature.

A contact transducer allows a direct measurement of the C_{44} component. This value is then used to define the constraints (u, v) on this component.

3 Experimental results for the 3D woven SiC/SiC

3.1 Tensile test coupled to microscopic observations

A series of monotonic tensile load coupled to an ultrasonic device has allowed the identification of the typical stress-strain curve of the composite (Fig. 5). This curve reveals four zones which characterising the damage development in the sample.

Microscopic observations of a polished face of one sample during a tensile test were used to link a density of transversal cracks to a corresponding stress state [8] (Fig. 5). Three areas of transversal damage (Fig. 6) are observed: i) matrix cracks between yarns, ii) cracks in the transversal yarns, iii) cracking in the longitudinal yarns. The transversal cracks in matrix and in the transversal yarns are located at the mesoscopic scale. In contrast, the cracks in the longitudinal yarn should be described at the microscopic scale.

Fig. 4. Loaded sample instrumented with the ultrasonic device used to investigate the damage of CMC.

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curve of a 3D-SiC/SiC: highlighting the four zones of damage. The O symbols are associated with the density of transversal cracks in the inter yarn matrix [0, 2, 4 and 6 cracks/mm] and within the transversal yarns [1.5 and 2.5 cracks/mm].

3.2 Stiffness change during a tensile test

Combining microscopic observations with the stress-strain curves and ultrasound measurements of the components of stiffness tensor leads to the identification of two main modes of fracture: cracking perpendicular to the load direction (transverse cracks) and interfacial debonding (fibre / matrix and yarn / matrix).

Fig. 7 plots the changes of the nine stiffness components identified as a function of the tensile applied stress.

The stress-strain curve exhibits a linear zone (Fig. 5: zone 1) for which the components of the stiffness tensor remain constant. Then, the curve takes the form of a "knee" (Fig. 5: zone 2) which is associated with the fall of the all diagonal stiffnesses involving the loading direction X_3 (Fig. 7): C_{33} , C_{44} and C_{55} . This loss of stiffness is related to the transversal cracks in the matrix inter-yarn and in the transversal yarn at the mesoscopic scale. The micrographic observations under loading (Fig. 6 (a) and (b)) allow measuring a density equals to 4 cracks/mm in the matrix inter-yarn and to 1.5 cracks/mm in the

transversal yarn at the end of the "knee" (Fig. 5).

When the stress-strain curve takes the form of a "plateau" (figure 5: zone 3), the mesoscopic cracks are stabilised and damage propagates within longitudinal yarns (Fig. 6 (c)). The C_{33} , C_{44} and C_{55} stiffnesses continue to decrease showing the growth of the transverse cracking in longitudinal yarn at a microscopic scale. In this zone, their decrease is associated with the fall of the diagonal stiffnesses involving the X_1 direction: C_{11} , C_{55} and C_{66} (Fig. 7). The damage in longitudinal yarn is linked to the debonding of the fibre- matrix interfaces.

Before the final fracture, the stress-strain curve stiffens again (Fig 5: zone 4) and the decrease of the diagonal components of the stiffness tensor stabilises. Saturation of the damage mechanisms is reached at the mesoscopic and microscopic scales.

The small variation in the stiffness C_{22} as a function of the applied stress (Fig. 7) shows that there is no development of cracks perpendicular to the direction X_2 . The increase in off-diagonal stiffnesses reveals the stiffening of the material to its lateral contraction during the loading.

Fig. 6. Micrograph images of the damage perpendicular to the loading direction, for the 3D-SiC/SiC composite: (a) inter yarn matrix cracks, (b) transversal yarn cracks and (c) longitudinal yarn cracks.

Fig. 7. Variation of the nine stiffness tensor components versus the applied stress as provided by ultrasonic measurement during a tensile test of a 3D-SiC/SiC specimen. The data are normalised by the initial values.

4. Modelling

The understanding of the mechanical behaviour of the composite cannot be made without an analysis at the microscopic level (yarn scale) and the mesoscopic level (woven scale). Thus, a multi-scale modelling is particularly appropriate for the mechanical analysis of this 3D woven CMC [9].

Micrographic and ultrasonic characterisation have shown that two crack arrays perpendicular and parallel to the loading direction must be considered. A first comparison between experimental and modelling results is performed with the help of finite element computation.

The Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the yarn is illustrated in Fig. 8. It consists of randomly distributed fibres surrounded by the matrix. Porosity is also introduced to reproduce the typical microstructure of the yarn. The fibres are assumed to behave like elastic isotropic materials but the multi-layered matrix is assumed to be a transversally isotropic material. The elastic properties of the yarn are then calculated with a periodic homogenisation procedure [9].

At the mesoscopic scale, a bidimensional cell is used. It reproduces the weave patterns of the composite and includes ten transverse yarns, ten longitudinal yarns in the thickness (X1 direction) and ten transverse yarns in length (X3 direction) with matrix layers and porosities (Fig. 9 (a)).

Fig. 8. Representative periodic cell of a yarn at the microscale: fibre, porosity and matrix. The different colors represent the different orientations of the anisotropic matrix.

Depending on their orientation within the woven composite, the elastic properties assigned to the yarns are deduced from the previous analysis at the microscopic scale.

To model the damage mechanisms, the observed crack arrays are inserted in the mesoscopic cell (Fig. 9 (b) and (c)) in order to estimate the damaged stiffness tensor with the help of a periodic homogenisation procedure.

In a first step, influence of cracks and debonding in the inter-yarn matrix is studied (Fig. 9 (b)). The maximum number of inter-yarn matrix cracks is selected based on micrographic observations of broken samples. The maximum length of debonding is extremely difficult to be measured by micrography and modelling will thus be used to quantify this unknown length.

The curves in Fig. 10 (a) represent the stiffness tensor variation with the crack density in the inter-yarn matrix. These results confirm the influence of transverse cracks on the stiffness C_{33} , the predominant influence of debonding cracks on the C_{11} component and the importance of coupling between the X_1 and X_3 directions on the C_{55} component.

The mesoscopic damage in the inter-yarn matrix is not sufficient to describe the loss of stiffness in the

composite. The change of the C_{11} stiffness shows that it is not justified to consider debonding length longer than 0.04 mm in the inter-yarn matrix, whereas in this state of cracking, the decrease of the components C_{33} and C_{55} , cannot be modelled.

Then, the length of the matrix/yarn interfacial debonding is taken to be 0.02 mm . In a second step, influence of cracks in transversal yarn is studied (Fig. 9 (c)). The maximum number of transversal yarn cracks is also chosen based on micrographic observations of broken samples. When the inter-yarn matrix cracking reaches 2 cracks/mm , it is observed that the crack density in transversal yarn gradually increases to 2.5 cracks/mm before sample failure (Fig. 5). The curves, in Fig. 10 (b), represent the components of the stiffness tensor as a function of the transversal crack density in the matrix inter-yarn and a variable density of transversal yarn cracks is now added. The density of transverse yarn cracking increases respectively from 0, 1.5 and 2.5 cracks/mm from top to bottom.

It is clear that the influence of cracks in the transverse yarn is small (Fig.10 (b)). But the addition of this crack area allows describing the decrease of the stiffness tensor components, i.e., the kinetics of damage until the “knee” of the stress-strain curve.

Fig. 9. Representative cells at the mesoscale: (a) initial mesh with matrix, longitudinal and transversal yarns, (b) mesh with matrix inter-yarn cracks and (c) mesh with transversal yarn cracking.

The calculated curves fit the first three experimental points represented by black symbols. Beyond 4 matrix inter-yarn cracks/mm, these two areas of cracking are not enough to describe the final experimental drop of the components C_{33} and C_{55} .

In a third step, influence of cracks and debonding in longitudinal yarns is studied. The maximum number of longitudinal yarn cracks is also chosen based on micrographic observations of broken samples. When the inter-yarn matrix cracking reaches 4 cracks/mm, it is observed that the crack density in longitudinal yarns gradually increases from 0 to 3 cracks/mm before sample failure.

The damage in the longitudinal yarn is simulated from the modelling of the material constituents at the microscopic scale and then is included in the 2D

mesoscopic cell.

The curves, in Fig. 11, represent the stiffness tensor components as a function of the transversal cracks density in the inter-yarn matrix. When the inter-yarn matrix cracking reaches 2 cracks/mm, cracks in transversal yarn are gradually added. When the inter yarn matrix cracking reaches 4 cracks/mm, the cracks in longitudinal yarn with variable length of debonding are added. Considering these three crack areas, it is thus possible to fit the change of the experimental stiffness tensor. The comparison between the stiffness tensor identified from acoustic measurements and the one obtained by the multi-scale damage modelling allows inferring that the debonding length in the longitudinal yarn must be around 0.1 mm.

Fig. 10. Modelling changes in the components of the stiffness tensor in the plane (X_1, X_3) versus the transversal crack density in the inter yarn matrix. The O symbols represent the experimental values measured by ultrasonic method.

(a) The grayscale corresponds to an increase of the length of the decohesions from 0 to 0.1 mm in step of 0.02 mm. The black curve is associated with cracks without debonding. The lightest gray corresponds to matrix transverse cracks associated with 0.1 mm of debonding. (b) When the density of the inter-yarn cracking matrix exceeds 2 cracks/mm, from the top to the bottom, the curves correspond to addition of 0, 1.5, 2.5 cracks/mm in the transversal yarns. The decohesion is set at 0.02 mm.

Fig. 11. Stiffnesses changes versus transversal crack density. When the density of the inter-yarn cracking matrix exceeds 2 cracks/*mm*, the transversal yarn cracking is added. The decohesion is set at 0.02 *mm*. When the density of the inter-yarn cracking matrix exceeds 4 cracks/*mm*, the longitudinal yarn cracking is added with a variable decohesion length. The grayscale corresponds to an increase of the length of the decohesions from 0 to 0.1 *mm* in step of 0.02 *mm*. The O symbols represent the experimental values measured by ultrasonic method.

Eventually using a full 3D model (Fig. 12) will probably underline the importance of the coupling between the different directions in the anisotropic behaviour of the composite.

Fig. 12. (a) Initial mesh at the 3D weaving scale. (b) Cracked mesh for a given damage state [10].

5. Conclusion

The non-linear mechanical behaviour of CMC involves the initiation and growth of micro-cracks. At a macroscopic scale, mechanics of damage can be associated with changes in the stiffness tensor components. By using an ultrasonic device coupled with a tensile machine, a spectro-interferometry method allows the characterisation of materials during their damaging and thus, the measurement of the state of material cracking.

Ultrasonic test results have yielded a typical behaviour of the 3D SiC/SiC composite. Two arrays of multi-scale cracks are detected: i) crack perpendicular to the load, i.e. the transverse cracking, ii) debonding on interfaces yarn / matrix or fibre / matrix.

The simultaneous use of ultrasonic characterisation results and micrographic observations under load lead to make assumptions about the kinetics of cracking of these materials: i) transverse matrix cracking between yarns, ii) superimposed on the transverse cracking of transversal yarns, iii) when those both arrays of cracking saturate, transverse cracking reaches the longitudinal yarns. This microscopic cracking array is coupled to matrix/fibre debonding.

The micrographic observations made during a tensile test have been used to estimate the density of transverse cracking versus the applied stress. The decohesion lengths are not measured but can be estimated by comparison with a multi-scale modelling.

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